

FORMATION OF GEOGRAPHY AS A SCIENCE

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Abstract: This article talks about the history of the formation of geographical knowledge, the formation of geographical science as a science, geographical works, the importance of the Great Geographical Discovery, and our great-grandfathers who wrote works on geography.

Keyword: Geographic knowledge, history, methodology of teaching geography.

The initial accumulation of geographical knowledge lasted until the 7th century BC. Geographical knowledge began to be used in connection with the needs of people during the primitive community. The first geographical knowledge of people consisted of finding a destination and making the simplest maps. The fact that people began to swim across the sea is considered a huge factor in the development of the science of geography. In particular, the Cretans' sailing across the Mediterranean Sea and crossing the Strait of Gibraltar to the Atlantic Ocean led to the creation of many geographical names. Such names can be called European and Asian. For the Cretans, it meant Europe to the west and Asia to the east. By the 7th century BC, the center of the development of the science of geography moved to ancient Greece. Many sciences were formed and developed in Greece. One of the famous scientists of this period is Homer. He created a world map in the 12th century BC. This map mainly depicts the surroundings of the Mediterranean Sea. The stage of formation of the science of geography. (from the 7th century BC to the 5th-6th centuries AD) at this stage, the development of shipbuilding expanded people's knowledge about the world and the emergence of large states, and the science of philosophy began to develop. Geography and other sciences began to develop within the framework of philosophy. By the 6th century BC, different opinions and views appeared about the formation of the earth. At this stage, Anaximan (6th century BC) drew a map of the world known to science and described the earth. Since then, major works on geography have been written. They replaced geographical textbooks. Aristotle proved the sphericity of the earth and the existence of heat regions on the earth in the 4th century BC. The world

map has been created. His card expands on the areas of Homer's card. On his map, a hot region inhabited by people and a cold region where people do not live are separated. The world map created by Aristotle depicts the northern part of Africa, the continents of Asia and Europe. India in Asia, Amudarya and Syrdarya, Caspian Sea, Italy in Europe, Macedonia, Inland (Mediterranean) Sea, Iberia and other places are described. Eratosthenes wrote the first textbook on the subject of geography in the 3rd century BC and introduced the term "geography" to the science. This textbook consists of three parts. In the first section, the history of the development of geography, in the second section, the dimensions of the Earth, land and ocean borders, climates are described, and in the third section, the division of the land into continents and oceans and the description of the major countries of that time are given. In addition, Eratosthenes made a world map and determined the dimensions of the Earth. At the end of the 2nd century BC and the first century AD, Strabo wrote a 17-volume work called "Geography". Geography of country studies was developed by Strabo. In the same period, Claudius and Ptolemy, who made a huge contribution to the development of the science of geography, lived. He invented the method of making geographical maps with a level grid. In this way he made a map of the world. He wrote the 8-volume work "Geography", the maps presented in his book are arranged in conic and stereographic projections. North is always depicted at the top of the cards. So, in ancient times, the term geography was introduced into science, a world map was created, and books and textbooks were written on the subject of geography. A method of leveling the cards has been invented. Fixed the representation of the north facing cards at the top. Development of geography education in the Middle Ages. In the Middle Ages, the science of geography and the methodology of its teaching developed and deepened. New books and textbooks were written, with the discovery of new lands, the map of the world began to become more defined. The development of geography education in the Middle Ages can be divided into 2 stages: the development of geography education in the first stage of the Middle Ages; the development of geography education in the stage of great geographical discoveries. The development of geography education in the first stage of the Middle Ages. At this stage, geography education developed mainly in eastern countries. At this stage of the development of geography education, the following results were obtained: In the VIII-IX centuries, Ahmad Al-Fargani created an astrolabe instrument. His astronomy textbook was used as a basic textbook in European countries for several centuries; Muhammad Ibn Al Khorazmi wrote a book called "Surat-al-Arz" in the 9th century; Abu Raykhan Beruni was the first to create a globe.

Made a map of the world. He made a great contribution to the development of geography. He wrote works called "India", "Mineralogy", "Monuments from ancient peoples", "Geodesy (mathematical geography)"; Abu Ali Ibn Sina reveals the role and importance of internal and external forces in the formation of relief; Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur made a great contribution to the development of regional geography with his work "Boburnoma". Based on the information presented in the work, it is possible to think about the natural conditions and economy of the countries of Central and South Asia in the Middle Ages. So, in the first part of the Middle Ages, geographical knowledge expanded and deepened. The stage of great geographical discoveries. From this stage, science began to develop again in Europe. As a result, discoveries of world importance were made. The American continent was discovered by Christopher Columbus in 1492. In 1498, the Portuguese expedition led by Vasco da Gama circumnavigated Africa and opened a sea route from Europe to India. In 1519-1521, the Spanish expedition led by Ferdinand Magellan made a round-the-world trip across the ocean and once again proved the sphericity of the earth. In 1650, the Dutch scientist B. Varenij wrote a work called "General Geography". In this work, geography is divided into two parts, that is, general and private parts. Development of geography education in the period of scientific geographical research. From the 17th century, special expeditions to study the nature of the Earth's surface began to be organized. Major scientific and practical results were obtained based on the collection of geographical data and their generalization. Geography was not taught as a separate subject until the middle of the 17th century. Geographical knowledge was given as part of country studies courses. Due to the influence of great geographical discoveries and the results of the stage of scientific geographical research, attention to the science of geography increased. As a result, from the second half of the 17th century, geography was included in the curriculum as a separate subject in the schools of Western European countries. Since the 18th century, geography has been taught in all schools. At the beginning of the 18th century, according to the specialization of schools, a certain branch of geography was taught. Mathematical geography was taught in navigation schools, and political geography was taught in others. Political geography mainly consists of descriptions of countries. At the beginning of the 18th century, a textbook was published by I. Guebner (1719). His textbook was called "Brief Description of the Globe". During this period, the great Dutch scientist Varenij wrote the famous work "General Geography". In the first half of the 18th century, geography teaching methodology developed in Holland and Germany. Many textbooks have been published. But the

content of these textbooks mainly consisted of geographical names, information and numbers. The students' activity consisted of memorizing them. M.V. Lomonosov made a great contribution to the development of geography and its teaching methodology in Russia. In the second half of the 18th century, Kh. Chebotarev published a textbook entitled "Geographical and methodological description of the Russian Empire." In this period, geography was taught in two classes: general geography in class III, geography of Russia in class IV. At the beginning of the 19th century, geography education was introduced in all educational institutions in European countries and Russia. The subject of geography is studied from the 3rd to the 8th grade of the 7th year gymnasiums. The amount of weekly hours for the subject of geography is 14 hours. In this period Ye.F. The subject of geography was studied according to the textbooks of Zavyalov, K.P.Arsenov. In the development of geography education in the second half of the 19th century, K.D. The works of Ushinsky, D.D. Semenov were important. K. D. Ushinsky developed several principles of teaching geography. D.D. Semenov wrote a textbook called "Geography Lessons". In the development of geography education at the end of the 19th century, the methodology of the German scientist Oberländer occupies a significant place. He wrote a textbook called "Methodology of Oberlander Geography". At the beginning of the 20th century, the works of D.N. Anuchin, N. Revsky, A. Sokolev, E. Petri, Ya. Rudnev, V. Budanov, S. Arzhanov and others were of great importance in the development of geography teaching methodology. The Oberlander methodology was further improved and developed by these scientists. Since the 20s of the 20th century, 9-year labor schools were established in Russia and the Commonwealth of Independent States (1st stage I-IV grades, second stage VI-IX grades), the purpose and content of geography education changed. 1921 D.N. A unified geography program was developed by Anuchin, before that each district and school had its own program. Geography of one's village, city, district in the III grade according to D. N. Anuchin's program; In class IV, the nature of different regions of the country; "Geography of continents" in grade V, geography of Russia in grades VI-VII, economic geography in grade VIII, astronomy and astrology in grade IX. In the 25-30s of the 20th century, attention to geography education decreased again. In 1924, schools switched to a new program, according to which no separate subjects were taught, but a complex of natural and social sciences was taught. From 1927-28, geography was again taught as a separate subject. The science of geography was taught in three parts: in the 3rd grade of elementary school, the natural geography of one's place of residence, in the 4th grade, natural zones, in the 5th grade, general

natural geography, in the 6th grade, the natural geography of the continents. geography, economic geography of the country in the 7th grade, the number of hours has been increased. In December 1958, the state made a decision about the school. Great attention was paid to studying the geography of his country. Institutes of scientific investigation were established, laboratories of geographical methodology were established in them.

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